

Artificial Intelligence is being used to Diagnose Disease through symptoms, geo-location, past treatment and climate and suggests prevention measures, past and present experiences and curing mechanisms

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ABSTRACT

Diseases are affected by the human body depending on Symptoms, Genes from the parents, Geo-location, past treatment and climate changes. So that with the help of Artificial Intelligence collects the information when patients take the treatment and analysis the situation of the patient and diagnose the disease. The Artificial Intelligence mechanism suggests the prevention measures and identifies the disease drug formula, suggest the drugs with percentage of success, past and present treatments given by the same doctor and other doctors with brief details of the patient other than security information and suggests the curing mechanisms.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Climate, Curing Mechanisms, Diseases, Drug Formula, Genes, Geo-Location, Symptoms.

Introduction

According to a study by Jon Hopkins, 250,000 people die every year in the United States because of medical errors, making medical errors the third largest cause of death after heart disease and cancer.

It is hard to diagnose diseases manually, machine learning plays a huge role in identifying the patient's disease, monitor his health, and suggest necessary steps to be taken in order to prevent it. It can include anything from minor diseases to major ones such as cancer which is tough to identify in the early stages.

While providing treatment to patients from the doctors check major information from the patient like Symptoms, Genes from the parents like parents having the same problem(s) in the past etc., Geo-location because soil, water problem(s), sanitation system in the geo-location

etc., previous treatments affect(s) present problem and climate changes. India and most of the countries are not maintaining diagnose reports of the patient(s) in hard copy or soft copy or in cloud storage. Due the above reasons providing treatment to the patient from doctor is difficult and sometimes failed in the process of treatment. If we collect the information when the doctor treatment happened to the patients and recorded in storage medium like cloud storage.

The collected data available in cloud storage, then training the data using Artificial Intelligence, Data Science and Machine learning algorithm(s), predicate the disease, suggests the prevention measures and identifies the disease drug formula, suggest the drugs with percentage of success, past and present treatments given by the same doctor and other doctors with brief details of the patient other than security information and suggests the curing mechanisms. So that doctor can provide treatment in a best possible way to the patient in a maximum extent.

Data Collection:

Using online doctor appointment system, we need to collect the patient information when they are taking treatment. Practo, Pluspin, curefit, lybrate, docprime, doctorserv(our product) under development are the available online platforms but the data collection and updating information is very less it is equal to less than 10%. If we improve the collection of collecting patient's information defiantly the treatments are very easy and getting better results.

In our product (Doctorserv), we are planning to collaborate doctors, medical shops, Diagnostics centers, Insurance agencies, Pharma companies in one platform. We are planning communicate and collaborate the 5 departments to provide services to the patients using technology gives better treatments in the society.

What is the issue / pain point that your product / solution addresses

Long queues at your Hospital's reception desk.

Long list of appointments on holidays.

Difficulty in rescheduling of booked appointments

Blockage of telephone lines due to excessive incoming calls.

Unordered appointment schedules due to lack of coordination between various source of appointment booking.

Receiving untimely calls in your home phone or mobile phone seeking appointments.

Difficult in maintains Patient records

Fig .01

Concept / Product / Technology Overview

Fig .02

Fig. 03

The collected information stores in cloud and use in a efficient way.

Training the data using Artificial Intelligence:

The collected data can be trained with the help of statistical algorithms and analysis the patients diseases. The below table .01 shows the sample data to identify the diseases with the following AI and Machine learning algorithms.

Diagnosis of Diseases by Using Different Machine Learning Algorithms

Many researchers have worked on different AI, machine learning algorithms for disease diagnosis. Researchers have been accepted that machine-learning algorithms work well in diagnosis of different diseases accurately.

S.No	Name of the Disease	AI or Machine learning Algorithm used to Diagnosis the Diseases
1	Hepatitis Disease	Naïve Bayes, Naïve Bayes Updateable, FT, K Star, J48, LMT, NN,C4.5, ID3, CART
2	Heart Disease	Bayes Net, SVM, FT, Naïve Bayes, J48, Bagging, GA+SVM
3	Diabetes Disease	Naïve Bayes, J48, CART, Adaboost, Logitboost, Gradding SVM, GA+Fuzzy Logic
4	Liver Disease	SVM, Navian Bayes, J48, MLP, Random Forest,

		Bayesian Network, Ksatr, FT Tree
5	Dengue Disease	DT, ANN, RS, SVM, MFNN
6	Joint detection in rheumatoid arthritis	Joint Localization, Active shape models, Manual, Colour and K-means image segmentation, Joint Localization, Contour delineation, ASM driven snakes
7	Cancer disease	PCA,ANN, Fractal dimension analysis ,DWT, Markov random process, Dogs-andRabbits algorithm
8	Lung diseases	FROC,ANN, Feed forward and Back propagation Neural Network
9	Alzheimer's disease	Naive Bayes FT K Star J48 LMT, NN, C4.5 ID3 CART
10	Parkinson disease	Boosted Logistic Regression, Gaussian radial basis function kernel based SVM, Linear LR NN SVM SMO Pegasos AdaBoost Additive L R Ensemble Selection FURIA Multinomial Ridge LR RF Bayesian LR

Table. 01

Suggests the prevention measures and identifies the disease drug formula:

Based on Disease, age, health metrics and other parameters AI and Machine Algorithms to generate drug formula that cures the patient. If possible instant drug preparation according the Disease cures the patient as early as possible.

Suggest the drugs with percentage of success:

Based on the above formula identify the available medicine in the market with success rate like disease name, name of the medicine and percentage of success rate.

Name of the Disease	Name of the Medicine	Percentage of success rate(Assumption)
Diabetes Disease Type 1	insulin lispro (Humalog)	56%
	insulin aspart (NovoLog)	78%
	insulin glulisine (Apidra)	80%
	regular insulin (Humulin R and Novolin R)	69%
	insulin isophane, also called NPH insulin (Humulin N and Novolin N)	92%
	insulin glargine (Toujeo)	89%
	insulin detemir (Levemir)	79%
	insulin degludec (Tresiba)	96%

Table. 02

In the table 02, we provide sample data like this we can show the drugs with success rate will help the doctor better and provide the medicine. After selecting the medicine by the doctor patient get the medicine details, no of quality, and nearest location the medicine available will be send to patient so that maximum risk factor will be reduced.

Past and present treatments given by the same doctor and other doctors with brief details of the patient other than security information & Suggests the curing mechanisms:

In the same window, we also display or show the past and present treatment by same doctor as well as other doctors and describe the treatment challenges and what course of action will be taken by them. How they are cured, how long it takes to cure will be known so that treatment done in best secure way.

Conclusion

I understood online platform necessary for getting better treatment, using Statistical models in AI and Machine learning for estimation of identifying the disease, identify the drug formula based on the information shows or display the medicine with success rate, past and present treatments with this online platform and Ai and Machine learning are the next biggest sources for healthcare industry.

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